

An Efficient Interworking Between Heterogeneous Networks Protocols and Multimedia Computing Applications

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Abstract— Nowadays, Multimedia Communication has been developed and improved rapidly to allow users to communicate between each other over the Internet. In general, the multimedia communication consists of audio, video and instant messages communication. The interworking between protocols is a very critical issue due to solving the communication problems between any two protocols, as well as it enables people around the world to talk with each other at anywhere and anytime even they use different protocols. Providing interoperability between different signaling protocols and multimedia applications will take the advantages of more than one protocol. This paper surveys the interworking functions between different VoIP protocols (i.e. InterAsterisk eXchange Protocol (IAX), Session Initiation Protocol (SIP), and H.323 protocol), Multimedia Conferencing System (MCS) (i.e. Real Time Switching Control Protocol (RSW) and Multipoint File Transfer System (MFTS), and multimedia applications (i.e. ISO MPEG-4 standards). At the end, a comparison among these protocols in terms of call setup format, media transport, codec, etc.

Keywords- *Multimedia; VoIP; Interworking; Instant messages (IM); Multimedia Conferencing Systems (MCS); InterAsterisk eXchange Protocol (IAX); Session Initiation Protocol (SIP); H.323 protocol; Multipoint File Transfer System (MFTS); Real Time Switching Control Criteria (RSW); ISO MPEG-4 standards*

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the last few years, the needs to provide the communication facilities among participants everywhere and every time via computer network systems have been increased. These network systems enable the use of multimedia applications (i.e. ISO MPEG-4 standards) [19] with many kinds of media data, such as audio, video, graphics, images, and text. This rapid expansion and potential underlies the significance of the interworking. Multimedia technology promises to make smooth and very effective interactions among people in different

geographical areas [33]. However, the provided multimedia services must be improved.

In recent years, Voice over IP (VoIP) technologies [37] has been developed and many significant progresses have been done in research and commercially. VoIP allows many users to make VoIP phone calls instead of the Public Switched Telephone Network (PSTN) through such technologies as InterAsterisk eXchange Protocol (IAX) [5], Session Initiation Protocol (SIP) [12], and H.323 protocol [25][26]. VoIP can offer a higher quality and yet more reasonable phone service than PSTN. The telecommunication industry is going towards using VoIP as their main phone infrastructure [37]. VoIP services become so popular in the last few years because it is inexpensive compared to the traditional telephony. VoIP can be integrated with other services, such as video conferences, instant messages and presence services.

On the other hand, instant messaging (IM) [29] is a form of online communication that provides a real-time interaction through personal computers or mobile computing devices. Users can transmit and receive messages privately, similar to e-mail, or join group conversations. It has become one of the most common and significant applications of the Internet, causing people to desire to stay connected to the Internet for a long time and allow them to exchange images, audio and video files, and other attachments [30] by using many protocols, such as EXtensible Messaging and Presence Protocol (XMPP) [31].

Multimedia Conferencing System (MCS) [7][8] is a system deals with the digital video, audio, and text data. It transfers these data in real time throughout the network as well as realizing the face-to-face visual meeting by utilizing the fine interactive and management function which are provided by computer system [21]. MCS uses the Real-time SWitching Control Protocol (RSW) [9] to handle a multipoint-to-multipoint multimedia conferencing sessions in terms of audio/video conferencing, whereas the

Multipoint File Transfer System (MFTS) [32][34] is used for the same purpose in terms of document conferencing.

Several signaling protocols and techniques are used to help bridging the gap between the endpoints, such as H.323 Protocol, SIP protocol [36], IAX protocol, RSW protocol, MFTS, XMPP protocol, etc. these protocols provides video, audio, data and instant messaging communication among participants [34]. In order to provide and enable the interworking between two or more dissimilar signaling protocols or standards, a translation module must exist in between in order to translate the different control options and instant messages transfer.

This paper is organized into 8 sections; **II** briefly describes the VoIP protocols. **III** describes the MCS protocols. **IV** explains the IM protocol. **V** discusses the ISO MPEG-4 standard as a multimedia application. In **VI**, we review some of the interworking studies between several protocols and multimedia applications. **VII** is a comparison among VoIP, MCS, IM, and multimedia application protocols. And **VIII** is a summary of this survey paper.

II. VOIP PROTOCOLS

A. Session Initiation Protocol (SIP)

SIP is an application-layer control protocol [11] that can establish, modify, and terminate multimedia sessions (conferences) such as Internet telephony calls [14][25][26][27]. SIP can also invite participants to already existing sessions, such as multicast conferences. Media can be added to (and removed from) an existing session. SIP transparently supports name mapping and redirection services, which supports personal mobility-users can maintain a single externally visible identifier regardless of their network location [12]. SIP protocol enables Internet endpoints (called user agents) to discover one another and to agree on a characterization of a session they would like to share. For locating prospective session participants, and for other functions, SIP enables the creation of an infrastructure of network hosts (called proxy servers) to which user agents can send registrations, invitations to sessions, and other requests. SIP is an agile, general-purpose tool for creating, modifying, and terminating sessions that works independently of underlying transport protocols and without dependency on the type of session that is being established [23][28].

SIP does not carry any voice or video data itself. It merely allows two endpoints to set up connection to transfer that traffic between each other via Real-time Transport Protocol (RTP) [3][37]. The User Datagram Protocol (UDP) [2] is a transport protocol used to transfer audio and video data [4]. SIP protocol has many features such as the service of text-based which allows easy implementation in object oriented programming languages, flexibility, extensibility,

less signaling, transport layer-protocol neutral and parallel search [22][23][24].

B. InterAsterisk eXchange Protocol (IAX)

In (2004) Mark Spencer [5] has created the Inter-Asterisk eXchange (IAX) protocol for asterisk that performs VoIP signaling. Streaming media is managed, controlled and transmitted through the Internet Protocol (IP) networks based on this protocol. Any type of streaming media could be used by this protocol. However, IP voice calls are basically being controlled by IAX protocol [14]. Furthermore, this protocol can be called as a peer to peer (P2P) protocol that performs two types of connections which are Voice over IP (VoIP) connections through the servers and Client-Server communication. IAX is currently changed to IAX2 which is the second version of the IAX protocol. The IAX2 has deprecated the original IAX protocol [5]. Call signaling and multimedia transport functions are supported by the IAX protocol. In the same session and by using IAX, Voice streams (multimedia and signaling) are conveyed. Furthermore, IAX supports the trunk connections concept for numerous calls. The bandwidth usage is reduced when this concept is being used because all the protocol overhead is shared for all the calls between two IAX nodes. Over a single link, IAX provides multiplexing channels [11].

IAX is a simple protocol in such a way Network Address Translation (NAT) traversal complications are avoided by it [8]. The Mini and Full frames are sent between two endpoints A and B. Each audio/video flow is of IAX Mini Frames (M frames) which contains 4 byte header. The flow is supplemented by periodic Full Frames (F Frames) includes synchronization information. UDP transport protocol is used by IAX to transfer audio and video data [4].

C. H.323 Protocol

H.323 is an umbrella standard that provides well-defined system architecture, and implementation guidelines that cover call set-up, call control, and the media used in the call [24][25][26]. It was established by the International Telecommunications Union (ITU) as the first communications protocol for real time multimedia communication over IP. H.323 takes the more telecommunications-oriented approach to voice/video over IP. H.323 protocol provides a comparable functionality using different mechanisms and offers highly network management and interoperability [27].

III. MULTIMEDIA CONFERENCING SYSTEM PROTOCOLS

A. Real-time Switching (RSW) Control Criteria

Real-time SWitching (RSW) control criteria is a control protocol used to handle a multipoint-to-multipoint

multimedia conferencing sessions. RSW control protocol was developed in 1993 as a control mechanism for conferencing by the Network Research Group in school of computer sciences, Universiti Sains Malaysia (USM) [9]. RTP protocol is used by RSW control protocol to carry audio and video data through multimedia conferencing. UDP transport protocol is also used by RSW to transfer audio and video data. The RSW control criteria is involved in decreasing bandwidth when many clients using the MCS system. RSW makes a list of priority for the participants to avoid confusion when many participants are trying to speak up during conference [6][13]. There are several advantages for the RSW control criteria [9] such as Equal Privileges, First Come First Serve, First come first serve with time-out, Organizer Main Site and Restricted Active site.

B. Multipoint File Transfer System (MFTS)

The Multipoint File Transfer System (MFTS) is a file distribution system based on the client-server architecture. The MFTS server is a distribution engine, which is responsible to handle the document transformation issues, such as file attachment, image sharing, and instant messaging exchange among the various MFTS clients. The Multimedia Conferencing System (MCS) [34] has adopted the MFTS product [35] for the Document Conferencing unit (DC), which is a network component that enables user communications related to file sharing and instant messaging interaction [32].

IV. INSTANT MESSAGING PROTOCOLS

The eXtensible Messaging and Presence Protocol (XMPP) [29] is a standard specified by the IETF for carrying instant message service. It is an open XML protocol for a real-time messaging, presence, and request/response services. First, Jabber open-source community proposed and introduced XMPP and it is still under the development. After that, the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) approved and archived it in many Internet specifications. The XMPP architecture consists of three elements, XMPP client, XMPP server and gateways to foreign networks. Transport Control Protocol (TCP) is used by XMPP to transmit and carry media sessions [30]. The developers have been added media session capabilities to XMPP clients which have been defined as an XMPP-specific negotiation protocol called Jingle [JINGLE]. However, Jingle has been designed to easily map to SIP for communication through gateways or other transformation mechanisms [39].

V. ISO MPEG-4 STANDARD: MULTIMEDIA APPLICATION

The recent ISO MPEG-4 standards [15][16][17] target a broad range of low-bit rates multimedia applications: from classical streaming video and TV broadcasting to a very interactive applications with dynamic audio-visual scene

customization. In order to reach this objective, advanced coding and formatting tools have been identified in the dissimilar components of the standard ISO 14496; such as audio, visual, and Systems, which can be constructed according to profiles and levels to meet several application needs. A core part of the MPEG-4 multimedia framework is the “Delivery Multimedia Integration Framework” [18]. DMIF provides content location independent methods for creating and controlling MPEG-4 audiovisual sessions and access individual media channels over RTP/UDP/IP.

VI. INTERWORKING BETWEEN HETEROGENEOUS PROTOCOLS AND MULTIMEDIA APPLICATIONS

This section will present many interworking studies between different protocols and multimedia client, such as SIP-H.323 interworking, SIP-ISO MPEG-4 interworking, IAX-RSW, etc.

A. SIP-H.323 Interworking

Because of the inherent differences between H.323 and SIP [24][25], accommodation must be made to allow interworking between the two protocols [10]. The proposed system model was established for simulating and verifying interworking between SIP and H.323. Five main components of this system are modeled by SDL/MSC: H.323 endpoint, H.323 gatekeeper, SIP-H.323 interworking facility, SIP server, SIP endpoint [21]. Figure 1 shows the architecture of the interworking between SIP and H.323.

Figure 1. SIP-H.323 Interworking Architecture [10]

B. SIP-XMPP Interworking

The Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) proposed an Internet-Draft working document [31] that specifies relevant requirement of enabling instant messaging interworking between the Session Initiation Protocol (SIP) and the Extensible Messaging and Presence protocol (XMPP) [29]. This Internet-Draft assumes that the interworking between the two standard protocols will be through a dedicated gateway protocol translator. Two gateways created namely “SIP-XMPP” and “XMPP-SIP”, the first one is used to translate from SIP specifications to XMPP specifications and is located in the SIP network domain, while the second

one is used to translate from XMPP specifications to SIP specifications and is located in the XMPP network domain [30]. Figure 2 depicts the architectural design of this interworking method.

Figure 2. SIP-XMPP Interworking Module Architecture [31]

C. SIP-MFTS Interworking

This study introduced a new IM interworking prototype between the Session Initiation Protocol (SIP) and the Multipoint File Transfer System (MFTS) [20][38]. The interworking system relies on adding a new network entity to enable the interworking which has the ability to work as a SIP server to the SIP-side of the network and as a MFTS server to the MFTS-side of the network. Both MFTS and SIP use the Transmission Control Protocol (TCP) for sending and receiving control messages (signaling) between their network components, the translation module should use TCP as well [20]. Figure 3 illustrates the general interworking system between SIP and MFTS.

Figure 3. SIP-MFTS Interoperability System [38]

D. SIP-ISO MPEG-4 DMIF Interworking

This study described the design and implementation of an experimental system for interworking between IETF SIP (Session Initiation Protocol) and ISO MPEG-4 DMIF (Delivery Multimedia Integration Framework) session and call control signaling protocols [19]. This IP video conferencing interworking system is composed of two core units for supporting delivery of audio-video streams from a

DMIF domain to a SIP domain (i.e. DMIF2SIP unit) and from a SIP domain to a DMIF domain (i.e. SIP2DMIF unit). These units perform various translation functions for transparent establishment and control of multimedia sessions across IP networking environment, including, session protocol conversion, service gateway conversion and address translation. Figure 4 illustrates the SIP-DMIF interworking.

Figure 4. Interworking between SIP and DMIF [19]

E. SIP-RSW Interworking

Because of the inherent differences between RSW and SIP [22], accommodation must be made to allow interworking between the two protocols. The interworking between RSW and SIP is essential to ensure full end-to-end connectivity [9]. This research proposed communication translation protocol to bridge the RSW control protocol and SIP control protocol. This communication translation protocol has to provide a set of rules to enable communications between the RSW control criteria and SIP standards. The communication translation entity defined is called translator server. Figure 5 shows an example of SIP-MCS session setup.

Figure 5. SIP to MCS Session Setup Example [9]

F. IAX- RSW Interworking

This study proposed the design of an experimental system for interworking between InterAsterisk eXchange Protocol (IAX) and Real-time SWitching (RSW) session and call control signaling protocols [1][6][7]. This IP videoconferencing interworking system is composed of two core units for supporting delivery of sessions and streams. These units perform various translation functions for transparent establishment and control of multimedia sessions across IP networking environment, including, session conversion, media conversion and address translation [8]. Figure 6 explains the architecture of the translation module.

Figure 6. IAX-RSW Interoperability Module Architecture [1]

VII. A COMPARISON AMONG SIP, H.323, IAX, RSW, XMPP, MFTS, AND DMIF PROTOCOLS.

In this section, we will compare among VoIP, MCS, IM, and multimedia application protocols in terms of call setup format, media transport, transport protocol, codec. Table 1 shows the comparison among the protocols.

TABLE I. A COMPARISON AMONG PROTOCOLS

	Call Setup	Transport Protocol	Media Transport	Codec
SIP	Invite→ ←200Ok Ack→	TCP/UDP	RTP/SRTP	Any IANA-Registered Codec
H.323	Setup→ ←Connect Ack→	TCP/UDP	RTP/SRTP	Any codec
IAX	New→ ←Accept Ack→	UDP	mini frame	G.711, GSM, G.723, etc
RSW	Create conf→ Notify→ ←Join	TCP/UDP	RTP	G.711, GSM, G.723, etc
MFTS	-	TCP	-	-
XMPP	Session- initiate→ ←IQ-result	TCP/UDP	RTP	G.711, Opus, Speex.
DMIF	DS_Session SetupRequest→ ←DS_Session SetupConfirm	UDP	RTP	G.711, G.723.

VIII. CONCLUSION

This paper surveys the previous interworking studies between different VoIP protocols (i.e. IAX, SIP, and H.323), MCS protocols (RSW and MFTS), IM protocols (XMPP), and multimedia applications (ISO MPEG-4 standards). In this paper, we briefly explained the privileges of each protocol and did some comparisons among them in terms of codec, transport protocol, call setup format, etc. We can observe that for each interworking between two different protocols, an interoperability module must be added in the middle of the two protocol clients. This module works as a translator between protocols, in order to understand each other even they use different formats and transport protocols when exchanging the data. As well as, this module enables people all over the world to communicate with each other regardless of the heterogeneity between the protocols. In the future, we hope that the researchers can interwork more than two protocols in order to take the advantages of many protocols, and this type of interworking will lead to more interactive and effective communications among participants.

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REFERENCES

- [1] H. S. Haj Aliwi, S. A. Alomari, and P. Sumari, "An Effective Method For Audio Translation between IAX and RSW Protocols," World Academy of Science, Engineering and Technology 59 2011, pp.253-256, 2011.
- [2] A. S. Tanenbaum, "Computer Networks," 4th edition, Pearson Education, Inc, 2003.
- [3] C. Perkins, "RTP: Audio and Video for the Internet," Addison Wesley, USA, 2003.
- [4] D. DiNicolò, "Transporting VoIP Traffic with UDP and RTP," 2007.
- [5] M. Spencer, and F. W. Miller, "IAX Protocol Description," 2004.
- [6] M. S. Kolhar, A. F. Bayan, T.C. Wan, O. Abouabdalla, and S. Ramadass, "Control and Media Session: IAX with RSW Control Criteria," Proceedings of International Conference on Network Applications, Protocols and Services, Executive Development Centre, Universiti Utara Malaysia, pp. 130-135, 2008.
- [7] M. S. Kolhar, A. F. Bayan, T.C. Wan, O. Abouabdalla, and S. Ramadass, "Multimedia Communication: RSW Control Protocol and IAX," The 5th International Symposium on High Capacity Optical Networks and Enabling Technologies, Penang, Malaysia, pp. 75-79, 2008.
- [8] M.S. Kolhar, M.M. Abu-Alhaj, O. Abouabdalla, T.C. Wan, and A. M Manasrah, "Comparative Evaluation and Analysis of IAX and RSW," International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security, pp. 250-252, 2009.
- [9] O. Abouabdalla, and S. Ramadass, "Enable Communication between the RSW Control Criteria and SIP Using R2SP," The 2nd International Conference on Distributed Frameworks for Multimedia Applications, pp. 1-7, 2006.

- [10] Radvision, "Overview of H.323-SIP interworking," © 2001 RADVISION Ltd, [www.radvision.com/NR/.../Overview of H323SIPInterworking.pdf](http://www.radvision.com/NR/.../Overview_of_H323SIPInterworking.pdf) (last accessed March 25, 2012), 2001.
- [11] P. Montoro, and E. Casilari, "A Comparative Study of VoIP Standards with Asterisk," Proceedings of the 2009 Fourth International Conference on Digital Telecommunications, pp. 1-6.
- [12] M. Handley, H. Schulzrinne, and E. Schooler, "SIP: session initiation protocol," Internet Draft, Internet Engineering Task Force, <http://www.ietf.org/rfc/rfc3261.txt> (last accessed Sep 25, 2011), 1998.
- [13] S. Ramadass, R.K. Subramanian, H. Guyennet, and M. Trehel, "Using RSW Control Criteria to Create a Distributed Environment for Multimedia Conferencing," Proceedings on Research and Development in Computer Science and its Applications, Penang, Malaysia, pp. 27-29, 1997.
- [14] T. Abbasi, S. Prasad, N. Seddigh, and Ioannis Lambadaris, "A Comparative Study of the SIP and IAX," Canadian Conference on Electrical and Computer Engineering, pp. 179- 183, 2005.
- [15] ISO/IEC 14496-1 "Coding of audio-visual objects --Part 1: Systems – final committee draft," May, 1998.
- [16] ISO/IEC 14496-2 "Coding of audio-visual objects – Part 2: Visual – final committee Draft," May, 1998.
- [17] ISO/IEC 14496-3 "Coding of audio-visual objects -- Part 3: Audio – final committee Draft," May, 1998.
- [18] ISO/IEC 14496-6 "Coding of audio-visual objects -- Part 6: Delivery Multimedia Integration Framework (DMIF) final committee draft," May, 1998.
- [19] A. Toufik, M. Ahmed, and B. Raouf, "Interworking between sip and mpeg-4 dmif for heterogeneous ip video conferencing," Proc. of the IEEE ICC, vol.25, no.1, pp. 2469–2473, Apr. 2002.
- [20] M.F Aboalmaaly, O.A. Abouabdalla, H. A. Albaroodi, and A.M. Manasrah, "Point-to-Point IM Interworking Session Between SIP and MFTS," (IJCSIS) International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security, pp. 84-87, 2010.
- [21] L. Wang, A. Agarwal, and J. W. Atwood, "Modeling and verification of interworking between sip and h.323," In Proceedings of Computer Networks, pp. 77 – 98, 2004.
- [22] M. Baklizi, N. Abdullah, O. Abouabdalla, and S. Ahmadpour, "SIP and RSW: A Comparative Evaluation Study," International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security, pp. 117-119, 2010.
- [23] Y. Zhang, "SIP-based VoIP network and its interworking with the PSTN," Electronics & Communication Engineering Journal, pp. 273-282, 2002.
- [24] I. Dalgic and H. Fang, "Comparison of H.323 and SIP for IP Telephony Signaling," in Proc. of Photonics East, (Boston, Massachusetts), SPIE, 1999.
- [25] P. Papageorgiou, "A Comparison of H.323 vs SIP," Master Thesis, University of Maryland at College Park, USA, 2001.
- [26] H. Schulzrinne and J. Rosenberg, "A Comparison of SIP and H.323 for Internet Telephony," In Proceedings of the 8th International Workshop on Network and Operating Systems Support for Digital Audio and Video (NOSSDAV'98), Cambridge, UK, pp. 83–86, 1998.
- [27] N. Networks, "A Comparison of H.323v4 and SIP," Technical Report, 3GPP S2, Japan, S2-000505, <http://www.cs.columbia.edu/sip/papers.html>, (Last accessed Sep 20, 2011), 2000.
- [28] A. B. Johnston, "SIP: Understanding the Session Initiation Protocol," Artech House, 2001.
- [29] P. Saint-Andre, "Extensible Messaging and Presence Protocol (XMPP)," RFC 3920, 2004. Core, Internet Engineering Task Force, 2004.
- [30] P. Saint-Andre, "Extensible Messaging and Presence Protocol (XMPP)," RFC 3921, 2004 Instant Messaging and Presence. Internet Engineering Task Force, 2004.
- [31] P. Saint-Andre, A. Hourri, and J. Hildebrand, "Interworking between the Session Initiation Protocol (SIP) and the Extensible Messaging and Presence Protocol (XMPP)," Core draft-saintandre-sip-xmpp-core-00, "Work In Progress", 2008.
- [32] S. Noori, S. Ramadass, R. Budiarto, and S. Rao, "A new algorithm for advanced file distribution system design," In Proceedings of International Conference on Information and Communication Technologies: From Theory to Applications, pp. 615- 616, 2004.
- [33] S. Ramadass, "A distributed architecture to support multimedia applications over the internet and corporate intranets," In proceedings of SEACOMM'98, Penang, Malaysia, 1998.
- [34] S. Ramadass and R. K. Subramaniam , "A control criteria to optimize collaborative document and multimedia conferencing bandwidth requirements," In Proceedings of IEEE Singapore International Conference on 'Electrotechnology 2000: Communications and Networks', Singapore, pp. 555-559, 1995.
- [35] S. Ramadass, S. Noori, R. Budiarto, and S. Rao, "Scalable and reliable multisession document sharing system," In Proceedings of 2004 International Conference on Information and Communication Technologies: From Theory to Applications, pp. 613-614, 2004.
- [36] D. Geneiatakis, T. Dagiuklas, G. Kambourakis, C. Lambrinouidakis, and S. Gritzalis, "Survey of security vulnerabilities in session initiation protocol," Communications Surveys & Tutorials, IEEE, pp. 68-81, 2006.
- [37] M. Adams & M. Kwon, "Vulnerabilities of the Real-Time Transport (RTP) Protocol for Voice over IP (VoIP) Traffic," Proceedings of the 6th IEEE Conference on Consumer Communications and Networking Conference, USA, pp.958-962, 2009.
- [38] M. F. EESSA, "Instant Messaging Interoperability Module between the Session Initiation Protocol (SIP) and the Multipoint File Transfer System (MFTS)," Master Thesis, USM, Penang, Malaysia, 2009.
- [39] S. Ludwig, J. Beda, P. Saint-Andre, R. McQueen, S. Egan, and J. Hildebrand, "Jingle," XSF XEP 0166, June 2007.

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